

Designing for Results in an Emerging Field

Using RECAP © to Interrogate the Space between Action & Results

Guest: Dr. Kathleen Pajer, M.D., M.P.H.
Client: Director, Precision Child and Youth Mental Health Collaboratory
Children’s Hospital of Eastern Ontario (CHEO) Research Institute

Context:

“ For our Precision Child and Youth Mental Health Collaboratory, we had a clear ambition—and some hypotheses about the kinds of activities that could get us there. But this is a complex program in a rapidly evolving landscape. In a new field like precision mental health, results don’t flow automatically from activities; the pathways between them shift as evidence, partners, and context change.

We used **RECAP©**—a tool grounded in Results-Based Management—to interrogate that “in-between” space. It gave us a structured way to surface and test the **risks, evidence** gaps, **contextual** realities, **assumptions**, and **people**-related factors that determine whether activities actually translate into results.

Application:

Original Results Pathway

Activity 1
Activity 2
Activity 3

Desired outcome:
Increased organizational capacity to create, manage, and govern multimodal health data systems.

Using RECAP©

Activity 1
Activity 2
Activity 3

Desired outcome:
Increased organizational capacity to create, manage, and govern multimodal health data systems.

- **Risk:** e.g., Data privacy
- **Evidence:** e.g., Research article by author X
- **Context:** e.g., Canadian & Indigenous data sovereignty
- **Assumption:** e.g., No major changes to AI regulation in Canada in the next 2 years
- **People:** e.g., Children & youth; clinicians, AI researchers

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